

Postanesthesia Handoff: A Quality Improvement Project

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Background

- Communication failures during transitions of patient care accounts for 80% of medical errors
- Human factors may lead to ineffective communication
- JACHO National Patient Safety Goal – Improved handoff communication

Problem Statement

Handoff has the potential for communication failures and threats to patient safety

Perioperative patients are at increased risk for communication failures

- High number of handoffs
- Handoffs transpire between providers of different disciplines
- Patient's physiological status is susceptible to potentially rapid and severe changes

Purpose

To improve patient handoff communication between anesthesia providers and postanesthesia care unit (PACU) staff

Methods

Design

- Quality improvement project

Setting

- Large non-profit county hospital

Sample

- Convenience, all anesthesia providers

Framework: Plan Do Check Act

Effectiveness of Checklist on Information Transfer

- Pre- to post-training overall transfer of information increased 65% to 69%
- Post-training checklist use was 11%
- In post-training observations transfer of information increased from 67% to 88% when the checklist was used, a 22% increase

Quality Metrics Related to Checklist Use

	Pre-training ¹	Post-training ²
Number of complete handoffs	0 (0%)	2 (3.6%)
Number of handoffs that included "Assess for readiness"	58 (85%)	44 (80%)
Number of handoffs that included "do you have any questions?"	24 (36%)	30 (55%)
	Pre-training³	Post-training³
Mean number of items transferred	12.33 (65%)	13.18 (69%)

¹n=67-68, ²n=55, ³n=[18-19] items on the checklist

Clinical Implications

- Rotation schedules and clinical needs are an important planning factor
- Further QI efforts aimed at improved communication and handoff standardization are necessary

Checklist

PACU Handoff Checklist

- ASSESS READINESS**
 - Are you ready for report?
- PATIENT INFORMATION**
 - Name
 - Age
 - ID verification
 - Allergies
 - Diagnosis/procedure
 - PMH and ASA Score
 - Language preference
- ANESTHESIA MANAGEMENT**
 - Type of Anesthesia
 - Lines/catheters
 - Intake/output
- KEY POINTS**
 - Anesthetic events/concerns
 - Surgical events/concerns
- MEDICATIONS**
 - Analgesia plan
 - Antiemetic plan
 - Antibiotics
 - Other medications
- CLARIFICATION**
 - Do you have any questions?

Recommendations

- Assess for barriers to implementation
- Research strategies to improve staff input and senior staff buy-in
- Consider incentives for phases throughout implementation
- Evaluate department culture